

DEVELOPMENT OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation. The article pays special attention to the development of entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan.

Keywords. history, entrepreneurship, small business Entrepreneurship is an initiative, within the framework of the current legislation, the activities of subjects of ownership aimed at the production of goods and the provision of services and making a profit or income.

The government pays great attention to the area of supporting women's entrepreneurship. In particular, large-scale work on the development of family entrepreneurship, ensuring employment of the population, supporting women's and youth initiatives is also being carried out within the framework of poverty reduction programs. The program "Every family is an entrepreneur" is being implemented in Uzbekistan.

Entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan has a centuries-old history, but entrepreneurship of its market forms, the process of creating industrial, trade, financial firms intensified at the end of the 19th century, when their number increased sharply. The centers of the cotton trade, where cotton firms, branches of various large banks were opened, became Tashkent, Samarkand, Andijan and others. 6 gins, steam engine.

It is noteworthy that the circle of large Uzbek entrepreneurs in the production and industrial sphere of capital investment is initially formed on the basis of the trade and commercial direction of economic activity. Back in the 1890s, old merchant dynasties began to invest their capital in the purchase and primary processing of cotton; in the real economic practice of Uzbekistan, the process of integrating the financial, commercial and industrial spheres of entrepreneurship began.

Moreover, this integration process as a result of its development has a concentration of capital, which increases its investment activity contributes to the development of the economy of our region. At the beginning of the twentieth century, far beyond the borders of Uzbekistan, the owners of large companies were known - Dautbaev, Khodzhaev, the Vadyaev brothers from the Fergana region, Fusailov, Kalantarov, Khakombaev from the Samarkand region, the Yaushev brothers, Asadullaev, Yusuf Davydov from Tashkent.

In connection with the rapid growth in the production and export of cotton from the fertile Fergana Valley in Kokand, Andijan, Asaka, Margelan,

trading and purchasing, sales companies, transport offices specializing in purchasing and export operations with cotton appeared. Unlike the Ferghana monopoly firms, in the Samarkand region, the Tashkent district, the Bukhara emirate, the Khiva khanate, such commercial structures did not have a clear specialization in cotton operations.

In addition to cotton, they were simultaneously engaged in the purchase and sale of all agricultural products, the sale of local and imported manufactured goods. The production of raw cotton, ginning, and through them, and other industries, trade of Turkestan were dependent on large monopoly commercial and industrial companies such as the Moscow Trade and Industrial Partnership for Trade with Persia and Central Asia, the Schlossberg Brothers Partnership, which hindered the development of local entrepreneurship, gave our economy a one-sided, agrarian-raw-material character.

Many of these firms had their own cotton processing plants in Tashkent. In 1912, in the Central Asian region, foreign firms owned 96 out of 256 factories, the rest were owned by local entrepreneurs who resold the absolute majority of refined cotton to the same foreign firms. At the same time, only some domestic entrepreneurial structures had their representations in the central cotton markets and exported fiber themselves outside Central Asia, experiencing very tough competition from monopolies.

But, despite this, many of our entrepreneurs have achieved significant success in business, contributing to the development of the economy of Uzbekistan with their active activities. Among those engaged in successful entrepreneurship at that time in our region was Yu. Davydov. He was not only engaged in the wholesale of manufactories in Moscow and Lodz factories in Tashkent, Adliye-Ata, Turkestan, but also built a modern cotton ginning and brewery.

Commercial, purchasing and marketing operations with cotton brought considerable income, which served as a condition and became the reason for the intensification of financial and banking activities in Uzbekistan in the late 1890s, when Russian and foreign banks directed their investment interests to the Central Asian region. In 1889, one branch of the State Bank functioned in Turkestan, in 1891 - 5 branches of commercial banks.

In 1912, 7 branches of the State Bank and 40 commercial banks provided financial services to domestic business circles in the Central Asian region. It should be noted that the strengthening of the lending and investment activity of banking capital in Uzbekistan did not hesitate to bring its positive results. So in

the Kokand district there was an oil refinery partnership "Rishtan" with an authorized capital of 130,000 rubles, in 1906 the Fergana oil and mining partnership "Chimion" was founded, the capital of which was estimated at 2 million rubles. By 1917, there were already hundreds of our entrepreneurs, who often had an annual turnover of up to one million rubles, in the Turkestan Territory.

Many of them became partners of foreign companies, were members of the training committee of the Central Asian branches of the State and commercial banks. Thus, the development of small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs), which is one of the priority areas in Uzbekistan's transition to market relations, did not begin in our country from scratch.

The entrepreneurial initiative of the Uzbek people is rooted in the historical past. In particular, already at the turn of the 19th-20th centuries, entrepreneurial structures of various business spheres began to actively form and function on the territory of Uzbekistan, having, in certain features, a fundamental similarity with the realities of today.

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